

A Study on Employee Job Satisfaction at Eid Parry Nellikuppam Cuddalore

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ABSTRACT

Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction is a measure of workers; contentedness with their job, whether or not they like the job or individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision. Job satisfaction can be measured in cognitive (evaluative), affective (or emotional), and behavioral components. Job Satisfaction is the favorableness or unfavorableness with which the employee views his work. It expresses the amount of agreement between one's expectation of the job and the rewards that the job provides. The objective of the study is to know about the employee job satisfaction factors, the relationship between gender and employee job satisfaction. Descriptive research method is used in the study. This study consists of both primary and secondary data. The tool used in this study is correlation. The population size is 50 and the sample size is 30. From the study it was found that there is no significant relationship between gender and employee job satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Job satisfaction, Gender of Employees, factors, Rewards, Nature of work, Recognition

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I. INTRODUCTION

(Vroom, 1964) defines "job satisfaction focuses on the role of the employee in the workplace. Thus he defines job satisfaction as affective orientations on the part of individuals toward work roles which they are presently occupying".

(Smith and Stone 1992) define "job satisfaction as employees' emotional state regarding the job, considering what they expected and what they actually got out of it. In fact, an employee with low expectations can be more satisfied with a certain job than someone who has high expectations. If one's expectations are met or exceeded by the job, then one is happy and satisfied with the job".

Locke (1969) who defines job satisfaction as feelings of contentment derived from the appraisal of one's job and the understanding that the job is assisting in achieving one's goals. Job dissatisfaction is the unpleasant affections that one feels if one appraises the job as a barrier in achieving one's values.

Hoppock (1935) defines job satisfaction as any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause a person truthfully to say I am satisfied with my job. According to this approach although job satisfaction is under the influence of many external factors, it remains something internal that has to do with the way how the employee feels. That is job satisfaction presents a set of factors that cause a feeling of satisfaction.

II. Objectives

1. To find the various factors that influence job satisfaction.
2. To find the relationship between gender and employee satisfaction

III. Hypothesis

1. There is no relationship between gender and employee satisfaction
2. There is relationship between gender and employee satisfaction.

IV. Literature review

Shaju, Subashini (2017) Organization often neglects the impact of job satisfaction towards the gravity of employee's performance. This study explains how do the multiple dimensions of job satisfaction are evaluated and further correlated with the job performance of the employees. Job satisfaction was observed higher in the supervisor's level rather than that of the employees in workers level. Also a greater range of job satisfaction is uncovered in employees with more job experience rather than those with less experience. The measures can be adopted for a better performance management system in the organizations and can be incorporated with these specifics for future compliances.

Raziq, Maulabakhsh (2014) Working environment has a positive impact on the Job satisfaction of employees. Bad working conditions restrict employees to portray their

capabilities and attain full potential, so it is imperative that the businesses realize the importance of good working environment. This research paper contributes towards the welfare of society as the results create awareness about the importance of good working environment for employee job satisfaction. The study impacts upon the future performance of businesses by taking working environment more seriously within their organizations to increase the motivation and commitment level of their employees. This way their work force can achieve better results. It also ensures that the employees of the organization will have the ease of working in a relaxed and free environment without burden or pressure that would cause their performance to decline. The progress that will be achieved in the business will directly help the economy of a country as developmental efforts will increase. In such conditions, the country will be able to handle the minor problems prevailing as it will be in a strong state to deal with them. The benefits of providing a good working environment to the employees are tremendous for both the organization and its employees.

Miah(2018) Although there is a certain limitation included in this study, the following conclusion will be providing some insights to manager to improve the level of employee job satisfaction. The analysis about employee job satisfaction researcher find the strong positive relationship with organizational performance. In addition, from the research we found that employees who are in higher levels tendency to more satisfy from intrinsic job satisfaction where employees who are working in lower position tendency to more satisfaction with extrinsic job satisfaction. From this study we also found that professionals or managers are willing to provide more effort to the job than non-managers. Furthermore, we found that those employees are older in company they are more satisfy compare to younger employees.

Harper, Elizabeth (2015) While the workers seem to be very satisfied with their jobs, identifying the factors associated

with job satisfaction is critical to successful strategies to improve retention and performance. Practitioners should focus on factors related to organizational and supervisory support. Efforts that assess and meet the training needs of new employees while building respect and trust from supervisors may be the most effective methods to ensure high levels of job satisfaction. Informal mentorship programs are one example of an initiative that addresses factors associated with organizational and supervisory support at low cost. Further research is needed to clearly identify and prioritize methods to improve organizational and supervisory support and how these factors relate to motivation, performance, and retention.

Rahman(2017) The job satisfaction levels of full-time direct sales agents of Takāful and insurance industry matter and have higher levels of job satisfaction associated with greater ranked efficiency, effectiveness, productivity and profitability, increases in job satisfaction have been linked to more positive work environments, improved culture, higher rate of worker retention, and finally with institutions identified as “Great Places to Work For”. The importance of job satisfaction in the insurance industry was the motivation for this examination of Herzberg’s two-factor theory with the moderating effects of Shari’ah perception.

V. Research methodology

Research is "creative and systematic work undertaken to increase the stock of knowledge, including knowledge of humans, culture and society, and the use of this stock of knowledge to devise new applications." Research design is defined as a framework of methods and techniques chosen by a researcher to combine various components of research in a reasonably logical manner so that the research problem is efficiently handled. Descriptive research is used in the study. The sample size is 30. The tool used in the study is correlation. The study consist of both primary and secondary. There is a significant relationship between gender and employee job satisfaction.

VI. Data analysis and intpretation

Table1 whether there is no relationship between gender and employee satisfaction.

RESPONDENT	X	Y	X-xi	y-yi	(x-x)^2	(y-y)^2	(x-x)(y-Y)
1	1	33	-0.4	33	0.16	1089	-13.2
2	1	36	-0.4	2.63	0.16	6.9169	-1.052
3	1	40	-0.4	6.63	0.16	43.9569	-2.652
4	2	38	0.6	4.63	0.36	21.4369	2.778
5	2	33.00	0.6	-0.37	0.36	0.1369	-0.222
6	1	26.00	-0.4	-7.37	0.16	54.3169	2.948
7	1	27.00	-0.4	-6.37	0.16	40.5769	2.548
8	1	38.00	-0.4	4.63	0.16	21.4369	-1.852
9	1	32.00	-0.4	-1.37	0.16	1.8769	0.548
10	2	33.00	0.6	-0.37	0.36	0.1369	-0.222
11	1	30.00	-0.4	-3.37	0.16	11.3569	1.348
12	2	32.00	0.6	-1.37	0.36	1.8769	-0.822
13	2	37.00	0.6	3.63	0.36	13.1769	2.178
14	1	25.00	-0.4	-8.37	0.16	70.0569	3.348
15	1	28.00	-0.4	-5.37	0.16	28.8369	2.148
16	1	33.00	-0.4	-0.37	0.16	0.1369	0.148
17	2	36.00	0.6	2.63	0.36	6.9169	1.578
18	2	36.00	0.6	2.63	0.36	6.9169	1.578
19	2	25.00	0.6	-8.37	0.36	70.0569	-5.022
20	1	37.00	-0.4	3.63	0.16	13.1769	-1.452
21	1	32.00	-0.4	-1.37	0.16	1.8769	0.548

22	2	43.00	0.6	9.63	0.36	92.7369	5.778
23	1	31.00	-0.4	-2.37	0.16	5.6169	0.948
24	1	36.00	-0.4	2.63	0.16	6.9169	-1.052
25	1	33.00	-0.4	-0.37	0.16	0.1369	0.148
26	2	37.00	0.6	3.63	0.36	13.1769	2.178
27	2	31.00	0.6	-2.37	0.36	5.6169	-1.422
28	2	36.00	0.6	2.63	0.36	6.9169	1.578
29	1	34.00	-0.4	0.63	0.16	0.3969	-0.252
30	1	33.00	-0.4	-0.37	0.16	0.1369	0.148
TOTAL	42	1001.00	0	33.27	7.2	1635.83	3.252

Coefficient of correlation $r = 0.029965$

The value of correlation $r = 0.029965$. This shows that there exists a positive correlation between gender and employee satisfaction. Hence we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. It was found that there is relationship between gender and employee satisfaction.

Table 2 showing the opinion of the respondents about satisfaction of job security

CATEGORY	NO OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
Satisfied	6	20%
Strongly satisfied	7	23.33%
Neutral	6	20%
Dissatisfied	6	20%
Strongly dissatisfied	5	16.67%

Source: primary data

From the above chart, it is inferred that 20% of the respondents are satisfied about the the job security, 23.33% of the respondents are strongly satisfied, 20% of the respondents are neutral, 20% of the respondents are dissatisfied and 16.67% of the respondents are strongly dissatisfied towards the satisfaction of the security.

VII. Findings

By using correlation it was found that $r = 0.029965$, there is a relationship between gender and employee satisfaction. 23.33% of the respondents are satisfied with the satisfaction of job security.

VIII. Suggestion

To motivate the employees, management can take into consideration some proper suggestions given by the employees, it will help to increase the motivation and ultimately job satisfaction of the employees. Management should provide proper security in the organization. So, the employees will be secured in the job. Technical and managerial training should be provided for each interval of time for growth of employees as well as in a great manner. Provision of reasonable wages plays an important role in improving the standard of living. This single factor is important for workers than any other. So, the company must provide adequate wages to the workers. Systematic planning reduces hurdles at workplace and it ensures smooth flow of work methods. So, the present method of planning the work would be maintained as before to attain the goals very effectively.

IX. Conclusion

Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction is a measure of workers' contentedness with their job, whether they like the job, individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision or not. Job satisfaction can be measured in cognitive, affective, and behavioral components. The object of the study is to know about the employee job

satisfaction and to find the relationship between gender and employee satisfaction. And I found by using correlation, there is positive relationship between the gender and employee satisfaction.

X. Reference

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